

Errors in estimation of both TMBHA and TCBHA are always less than 1.0%. (Maximum errors were $\pm 0.7\%$ and $\pm 0.6\%$ for TMBHA and TCBHA respectively). The method can be used to estimate quantitatively 1-20 mg of benzohydroxamic acids.

Potentiometric titrations give the most accurate results but the method requires longer time. Enthalpimetric titrations are much simpler and quicker than the other methods and give quite satisfactory results. Enthalpimetric titration is therefore recommended for quick estimation of benzohydroxamic acids upto 12 mg in routine work.

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Titrimetric Determination of Ascorbic Acid with Chloramine-T using Oxazine Dyes as Indicators†

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VERY few indicators have been reported for the titrimetric determination of ascorbic acid with chloramine-T and these are starch¹, variamine blue², cacotheline³ and N-substituted phenothiazines⁴. We have now investigated the use of seven

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oxazine dyes, Capri Blue (CB), Solochrome Prune AS (SPAS), Gallamine Blue (GB), Celestine Blue (CLB), Meldola's Blue (MB) (Colour Index Nos. 51015, 51040, 51045, 51050 and 51175 respectively), Cresyl Fast Violet Acetate (CFVA) and Resazurin (RSZ) as indicators in this titrimetric determination in neutral and hydrochloric, acetic and sulphuric acid media. The titrations can be performed satisfactorily in (1) neutral medium employing CB, SPAS, GB, CLB and RSZ, (2) hydrochloric acid medium using CB, SPAS, GB and CLB and (3) acetic acid medium using SPAS, GB and CLB as indicators. The titrations cannot be performed in sulphuric acid medium. The method employing hydrochloric acid as titration medium and CB, SPAS, GB and CLB as indicators can be applied for the determination of ascorbic acid content of commercial pharmaceuticals.

Experimental

Approximately 0.1 N solutions of chloramine-T and ascorbic acid (0.5 g of EDTA per litre was used as stabiliser) were prepared and standardised as per accepted methods. Dye solutions (0.1%) were prepared in deionised water from the following samples: CB (Chroma); SPAS, GB, CLB, MB and CFVA (E. Gurr); RSZ (B. D. H.). Other chemicals were of reagent grade quality.

Procedure: Ascorbic acid solution (4-10 ml of 0.1 N) is treated with sufficient water or 1 : 1 hydrochloric or acetic acid and diluted to 50 ml. 1 ml of 0.1 M potassium bromide and 0.2 ml of 0.1% indicator solution are added and the mixture titrated with the chloramine-T solution. The conditions of the titrations are as follows:

Hydrochloric acid medium: CB: 1.5-4.0 M; SPAS: 0.5-2.5 M; GB: 0.5-1.5 M; CLB: 0.5-2.0 M.

Acetic acid medium: SPAS, GB and CLB: 0.04-1.0 M.

The colour changes at the end points are:

Neutral medium: CB: dark blue to pale blue; SPAS: bluish violet to colourless; GB and CLB: violet to colourless; RSZ: pink to colourless.

Hydrochloric and acetic acid media: CB: Green to colourless; SPAS, GB and CLB: pink to colourless.

The method developed for titration in hydrochloric acid medium can be utilised for the determination of ascorbic acid contents of commercial pharmaceutical preparations as per the procedure described by Rao *et al*⁵.

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